

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

DEVELOPMENT OF NOVEL CO-PROCESSED EXCIPIENTS FOR THE DESIGN OF FAST DISSOLVING TABLETS

Sunil Aute, S B Shirsand, Shailashri, Amruta and S A Baig

Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, H.K.E. Society's College of Pharmacy, Sedam Road, Gulbarga- 585 105, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 15/05/2019

Available online
30/09/2019

Keywords

Repaglinide;
Co-Processed Excipients;
Spray Drying;
Microcrystalline Cellulose;
Mannitol;
Aerosil.

ABSTRACT

Co-processed excipients were prepared by Spray drying. In Spray drying method, MCC: Mannitol: Aerosil in different ratios (26:70:4, 28:70:2 and 30:70:0) were used. The developed excipients were evaluated for compressibility index (Carr's index), Hausner's ratio and flow properties (angle of repose) in comparison with physical mixture of the excipients. The angle of repose of Co-processed excipients was found to be $<30^\circ$ which indicate good flow in comparison to physical mixture of the excipients, due to micronization, a very regular particle size is achieved, Carr's index in the range of 8.00-12.00% and Hausner's ratio in the range of 1.00-1.13. Fast dissolving tablets of Repaglinide were prepared using the above Novel co-processed excipients and evaluated for pre-compression and post-compression parameters. Among the tablets prepared, the Novel Co-processed formulations MCC: Mannitol: Aerosil in (26:70:4) ratio was found to be promising and displayed a dispersion time of approximately 30.66 s. Wetting time was found to be 29.66 s. which facilities its faster dispersion in the mouth. Stability studies of promising formulations indicated that there are no significant changes in drug content and *in vitro* dispersion time. IR-spectroscopic studies indicated that there are no drug-excipient interactions. It can be concluded from the present work that co-processed excipients used in Repaglinide fast dissolving tablets were found to be superior in flow characteristics in comparison with the physical mixture of same excipients.

Corresponding author

Sunil Aute

Department of Pharmaceutical Technology,
H.K.E. Society's College of Pharmacy,
Sedam Road, Gulbarga- 585 105, India.
sunilaute@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Sunil Aute et al.** Development of Novel Co-Processed Excipients for the Design of Fast Dissolving Tablets. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2019;9(09).

Copy right © 2019 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

www.iajpr.com

INTRODUCTION

Major challenge for tablets and capsule manufacturing comes from the flow properties of the materials to be compressed. Most of the formulations (>70%) contain excipients at higher concentration than active drug.^[1] In recent years drug formulation scientists have recognized that single-component excipients do not always provide the requisite performance to allow certain active pharmaceutical ingredients to be formulated or manufactured adequately.^[2] Hence, there is a need to have excipients with multiple characteristics built into them such as better flow, low/no moisture sensitivity, superior compressibility and rapid disintegration ability.^[3] One such approach for improving the functionality of excipients is co-processing of two or more excipients.

Co-processing is based on the novel concept of two or more excipients interacting at the sub particle level, the objective of which is to provide a synergy of functionality improvement as well as masking the undesirable properties of individual.^[4] Co-processing excipients leads to the formulation of excipient granules with superior properties compared with physical mixtures of components or individual components.^[5] The concept of formulating fast dissolving tablets (FDT) of Repaglinide (antidiabetic) using co-processed excipients which increase the water uptake with shortest wetting time and thereby decrease the disintegration time of the tablets by simple and cost effective (at low concentration of excipients) direct compression technique.^[6-8]

MATERIALS

Repaglinide was a gift sample from Torrent Pharmaceuticals, Sikkim Plant. Mannitol was a gift sample from Strides Arco Labs, Bangalore. Aerosil was gift sample from Alkem Labs Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai India. All the other chemicals were of analytical grade.

DEVELOPMENT OF CO-PROCESSED EXCIPIENTS⁹

Development of Co-processed Excipients by Spray Drying Method:

Procedure:

Co-processed excipients were prepared by using spray-drying technique using a laboratory spray dryer (Model SPD-P-111; Technosearch Instruments, India) with a standard 0.7 mm nozzle. Different batches of co processed excipients were prepared by dissolving the different ratios of polymer MCC: Mannitol: Aerosil (26:70:4, 28:70:2 and 30:70:0) in Dimethyl formamide (DMF) under constant stirring at 500 rpm for 2 h using a magnetic stirrer. When the polymer Dimethyl formamide (DMF) solution was fed to the nozzle with a peristaltic pump, the atomization occurred by the force of compressed air, disrupting the Dimethyl formamide (DMF) solution into small droplets. The droplets, together with hot air, were blown into the drying chamber, where the solvent in the droplets was evaporated and discharged out through an exhaust tube. The co processed excipients were collected from cyclone 1 and cyclone 2, washed with distilled to remove surface adhered excipients and further dried completely in hot air oven at 40°C for 12 h and stored in a well-closed container.

The processing conditions of the spray drying were:

Inlet Temperature: 165°C

Outlet temperature: 120°C

Feed pump rate: 2ml/min

Spray pressure atomization: 2×10^5 PC.

Preparation of fast dissolving tablets of Repaglinide by direct compression method:

Fast dissolving tablets of Repaglinide were prepared by direct compression according to the formulae given in Table-1. All the ingredients were passed through 60 mesh sieve separately. The drug and MCC was mixed by small portion of both each time and blending it to get a uniform mixture and kept aside. Then the ingredients were weighed and mixed in geometrical order and tablets were compressed at 7 mm size to get a tablet of 150 mg weight using a Rotary Clit 10 station compression machine.^[10]

Evaluation of Physically mixed Excipients/Co-processed Excipients:

The developed excipients were evaluated for compressibility index (Carr's index), Hausner's ratio and flow properties (angle of repose) in comparison with physical mixture of excipients shown in Table-2.

Evaluation of fast dissolving tablets:

The prepared batches of formulations were evaluated post compression parameters such as drug content uniformity, weight variation, hardness, friability, thickness, *in vitro* dispersion time, *in vitro* drug release and stability studies (given in Table-3).

Weight Variation:

The weight of the tablet being made was routinely determined to ensure that a tablet contains the proper amount of drug. The USP weight variation test is done by, twenty tablets were selected at random and weighed individually, and the individual weights were compared with average weight for the determination of weight variation.^[11]

Thickness variation:

Thickness of the tablet is important for uniformity of tablet size. Thickness was measured using Vernier Calipers. It was determined by checking the thickness of three tablets of each formulation.

Tablet Hardness and Friability:

The resistance of tablets to shipping or breakage under conditions of storage, transportation and handling before usage depends on its hardness. The hardness of each batch of tablet was checked by using digital hardness tester. The hardness was measured in terms of kg/cm². Three tablets were chosen randomly and tested for hardness. The average hardness of 3 determinations was recorded. Friability generally refers to loss in weight of tablets in the containers due to removal of fines from the tablet surface. Friability generally reflects poor cohesion of tablet ingredients. Ten tablets were weighed and the initial weight of these tablets was recorded and placed in Roche friabilator and rotated at the speed of 25 rpm for 100 revolutions. Then tablets were removed from the friabilator, dusted off the fines and again weighed and the weight was recorded.

Drug Content Uniformity:

Ten tablets were weighed and powdered, a quantity of powder equivalent to 1 mg of Repaglinide was transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask and 40 ml methanol is added. The drug is extracted into the methanol by vigorously shaking the stoppered flask for 15 minutes. Then the volume is adjusted to 50 ml with methanol and the liquid is filtered. The Repaglinide content was determined by measuring the absorbance at 237 nm. after appropriate dilution with methanol. The drug content was calculated using the standard calibration curve. The mean percent drug content was calculated as an average of three determinations.^[12]

Wetting Time and Water Absorption Ratio:

A piece of tissue paper folded twice was placed in a small Petri dish containing 6 ml of water. A tablet was put on the paper and the time required for complete wetting was measured. The wetted tablet was then weighed (given in Table-3).^[13]

Water absorption ratio 'R' was determined using following equation:

$$R = 100 \times (W_a - W_b/W_b)$$

Where,

W_a = weight of tablet before water absorption,

W_b = weight of tablet after water absorption.

In vitro Dispersion Time:

Tablet was added to 10 ml of phosphate buffer solution, pH 6.8 at 37±0.5°C. Time required for complete dispersion of a tablet was measured (given in Table-3).^[14]

In vitro Dissolution Study:

In vitro dissolution of a Repaglinide fast disintegrating tablet was studied in USP type-II dissolution apparatus (Electrolab) employing a paddle stirrer. 900 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was used as dissolution medium. The stirrer was adjusted to rotate at 50 rpm. The temperature of dissolution media was previously warmed to 37±0.5°C and was maintained throughout the experiment. One tablet was used in each test. 5 ml of sample of dissolution medium were withdrawn by means of syringe fitted with pre-filter at known intervals of time and analyzed for drug release by measuring the absorbance at 241 nm. The volume withdrawn at each time interval was replaced with fresh quantity of dissolution medium. Percentage amount of Repaglinide released was calculated and plotted against time. For comparison the dissolution of Repaglinide from commercial formulation was also studied.

Accelerated Stability Studies:

Stability studies on the promising formulation (MCMA₁) were carried out by storing 15 tablets in amber colored screw capped bottle at elevated temperature of 40°C/ 75% RH over a period of 3 months. At interval of 1 month, the tablets were visually examined for any physical changes, changes in drug content and in vitro dispersion time.

Table-1: Formulations of Repaglinide Fast Dissolving Tablets.

Ingredients (mg/tablet)	Formulation Code			
	CP ₀	MCMA ₁	MCMA ₂	MCMA ₃
Repaglinide	1	1	1	1
Co-processed Excipients	-	12	12	12
Aspartame	3	3	3	3
Sodium stearyl fumarate	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Talc	3	3	3	3
Pine apple Flavour	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
MCC (Avicel PH-102)	30	30	30	30
Mannitol (Pearlitol SD 200)	110	98	98	98
Total Weight	150	150	150	150

CP₀-Control formulation (without Co-processed excipients).

MCMA Indicates: Microcrystalline cellulose, Mannitol & Aerosil.

Table-2: Pre-compression Parameters of physically mixed excipients/Co-processed Excipients.

Parameters	Formulation Code					
	PMCMA ₁	MCMA ₁	PMCMA ₂	MCMA ₂	PMCMA ₃	MCMA ₃
Bulk density (g/cc)	0.45	0.52	0.45	0.52	0.43	0.51
Tapped density (g/cc)	0.54	0.56	0.55	0.57	0.52	0.58
Angle of repose (degree) ^o	25.35	20.17	28.39	22.00	29.35	23.80
Carr's index (%)	16.35	08.13	18.18	09.88	17.40	12.00
Hausner's Ratio	1.20	01.08	1.22	01.10	1.21	01.13

Table-3: Post-compression Parameters of Repaglinide Fast Dissolving Tablet formulations.

Parameters→ Formulation Code ↓	Hardness (kg/cm ²)* ±SD	Friability (%)	Thickness* (mm)	In vitro dispersion time (s)* ±SD	Wetting time (s)* ± SD	Water absorption ratio (%)* ±SD	Percent drug content (%)* ±SD	Weight variation (%)
CP ₀	2.5±0.10	0.33	2.60±0.17	122±4.35	115±2.00	56.86±1.40	99.45±0.01	142-158
MCMA ₁	2.40±0.28	0.68	2.46±0.30	30.66±1.54	29.66±2.51	94.65±1.32	99.44±0.07	mg (IP
MCMA ₂	2.43±0.15	0.59	2.53±0.15	35.33±2.08	33.33±2.64	89.26±0.75	99.45±1.01	limits ±
MCMA ₃	2.46±0.20	0.61	2.63±0.11	40.00±1.73	38.33±2.08	88.13±0.61	99.40±1.02	7.5%)

*Average of three determinations.

Table-4: Comparative *in vitro* Dissolution parameters of control, commercial and promising formulations in pH 6.8 Phosphate Buffer.

Parameters

Formulation code	D ₅	D ₁₀	D ₁₅	t _{50%}	t _{70%}	t _{90%}	DE _{10min}
CP ₀	27%	50%	57%	10 min	>30 min	>30 min	26.69%
MCMA ₁	76%	95%	--	1.4 min	3.4 min	8.8 min	70.36%
CCF	26%	50%	56%	10 min	>30 min	>30 min	25.21%

CP₀ is control formulation, MCMA₁ is promising fast dissolving tablet formulation, CCF is conventional commercial tablet formulation, D₅ is percent drug released in 5 min, D₁₀ is percent drug release in 10 min, D₁₅ is percent drug release in 15 min, DE_{10min} is dissolution efficiency at 10 min, t_{50%} is time for 50% drug dissolution, t_{70%} is time for 70% drug dissolution, t_{90%} is time for 90% drug dissolution.

FIGURE:-1: Comparative cumulative percent drug release versus time plot (zero order) of control formulation, promising tablet formulations of Repaglinide and Commercial Conventional Formulation CCF in phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Co-processed excipients were prepared by spray drying using co processed excipients MCC: Mannitol: Aerosil in (26:70:4, 28:70:2 and 30:70:0). The co-processed excipients were evaluated for their flow and compression properties in comparison with physical mixture of excipients. The angle of repose of co-processed excipients was found to be $<30^\circ$ which indicate excellent flow in comparison to physical mixture of excipients (near to 30°) due to granule formation, Carr's index in the range of 8.00-12.00% and Hausner's ratio in the range of 1.00-1.13 (Table-2).

Fast dissolving tablets of Repaglinide were prepared using above co-processed excipients. A total of 3 formulations and control formulation CP₀ (without excipients) were designed. As the blends were free flowing (angle of repose $<30^\circ$ and Carr's index $<15\%$ Table-2), tablets obtained were of uniform weight (due to uniform die fill), with acceptable variation as per IP specification i.e., below 7.5%. Drug content was found to be in the range of 99.40 to 99.44%, which is within acceptable limits. Hardness of the tablets was found to be in the range of 2.40-2.46 kg/cm². Friability below 1% was an indication of good mechanical resistance of the tablets. Water absorption ratio and wetting time, which are important criteria for understanding the capacity of excipients to swell in presence of little amount of water were found to be in the range of 88.13-94.65% and 29.66-38.33 sec respectively. Among the tablets prepared, Co-processed formulations MCMA₁ containing MCC: Mannitol: Aerosil in different ratios (26:70:4) found to be promising and has shown an in vitro dispersion time of 30.66 s, wetting time of 29.66 s, and water absorption ratio of 94.65% and control formulation (CP₀) shows 122 s, 115 s, and 56.86% values respectively for the above parameters (Table-3). In vitro dissolution studies on the promising formulation MCMA₁, control (CP₀) and commercial conventional formulations (CCF) were carried out in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, and the various dissolution parameter values viz., percent drug dissolved in 5, 10 and 15 min (D₅, D₁₀ and D₁₅), dissolution efficiency at 10 min (DE₁₀ min), t_{50%}, t_{70%} and t_{90%} are shown in Table-4 and dissolution profile depicted in fig 1. This data reveals that overall, the formulation MCMA₁ has shown more than seven fold faster drug release when compared to the commercial conventional tablet formulation of Repaglinide (t_{50%} in 1.40 min). IR spectroscopic studies indicated that the drug is compatible with all the excipients. The IR spectrum of MCMA₁ showed all the characteristic peaks of Repaglinide pure drug, thus confirming that no interaction of drug occurred with the components of the formulation. Stability studies of the above formulations indicated that there are no significant changes in drug content and in vitro dispersion time at the end of 3 months period (p <0.05).

CONCLUSION

Repaglinide tablets containing co-processed excipients exhibited good flow and compression characteristics. Repaglinide tablets containing co-processed excipients exhibited quick disintegration and improved drug dissolution. It can be concluded from the present work that co-processed excipients of MCC, Mannitol and Aerosil are superior to physical mixture of MCC, Mannitol and Aerosil. The developed co-processed excipients may be used in the future research for the development of novel solid dosage forms

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to Torrent Pharmaceuticals, Sikkim Plant, India for providing gift sample of Repaglinide. The authors are also thankful to Stride Arco Lab, Bangalore, Karnataka, India and Alkem Labs Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, Maharashtra, India for providing gift sample of Mannitol, Aerosil and Micro-crystalline cellulose respectively. The authors are very grateful to management and staff of H.K.E. Society's College of Pharmacy, Gulbarga, Karnataka for providing facilities to carry out the work.

Conflict of interest- None

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS USED

CCF	Commercial conventional formulation
FDT	Fast dissolving tablet
MCC	Microcrystalline cellulose
Min	Minutes
Rpm	Revolutions per minute
S	Seconds
SD	Standard deviation
w/w	Weight by weight

REFERENCES

1. York, P. 1992. Crystal engineering and particle design for the powder compaction process. *Drug. Dev. and Ind. Pharm.* 18, 677-721.
2. Block, L.H. 2009. Co-processed excipients. *Pharmacoepial. Forum.* 35, 1026-1028.
3. Avachat, A. and Ahire, V.J. 2007. Characterization and evaluation of spray dried co-processed excipients and their application in solid dosage forms. *Indian. J. Pharm. Sci.* 69, 85-90.
4. Reimerdes, D. 1993. The near future of tablet excipients. *Manuf. Chem.* 64, 14-15.
5. Jacob, S., Shirwaikar A.A., Joseph, A. and Srinivasan, K. 2007. Novel co-processed excipients of mannitol and microcrystalline cellulose for preparing fast dissolving tablets of Glipizide. *Indian. J. Pharm. Sci.* 69, 633-639.
6. Sweetman SC, editor. *Martindale: The complete Drug Reference*, 35th edn. Pharmaceutical Press, London: 2007:p415.
7. https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2009/020741s0351bl.pdf
8. <https://www.drugbank.ca/drugs/DB00912>
9. T. Tripathy and R. P. Singh. 2000. High performance flocculating agent based on partially hydrolysed sodium alginate-g-polyacrylamide. *Eur. Polym. J.* 36, 1471.
10. Kuchekar BS, Badhan AC, Mahajan HS. Mouth dissolving tablets of salbutamol sulphate: A novel drug delivery system. *Indian Drugs* 2004; 41: 592-8.
11. Bankar, G.S., Anderson, N.R. Tablets. In: Lachman L, Lieberman H.A. and Kanig JL. 1987, editor. *The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy*. 3rd ed., Mumbai: Varghese Publishing House, pp. 293-299.
12. *Indian Pharmacopoeia*, 4th ed, Vol. II: Controller of Publications, Govt. of India, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, New Delhi; 1996: 735.
13. Chaudhari PD, Chaudhari SP, Kolhe SR, Dave KV, More DM. Formulation and Evaluation of fast dissolving tablets of famotidine. *Indian Drugs* 2005; 42(10): 641-9.
14. Bhagwati, S.T., Hiremath, SN. and Sreenivas, S.A. 2005. Comparative evaluation of disintegrants by formulating cefixime dispersible tablets. *Indian. J. Pharm. Edu. Res.* 39, 194-197.

54878478451190301

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

